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A SYSTEMATIC STUDY OF DIGITAL MARKETING AS A COMPETITIVE TECHNOLOGY-BASED APPROACH

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Abstract:

Digital marketing is an excellence to market products or services using new technologies, especially on the Internet, but frequently on smartphones, displays and other digital platforms. The way digital marketing has progressed since the 1990s and 2000s has transformed the use of technology and digital marketing by products and organisations to market. Digital marketing strategies are quick and effective as digital channels are increasingly integrated into the marketing strategy and everyday life, and digital devices are used by people rather than traditional shops.

Keywords: Marketing of content, marketing, new technology, sales on the Internet.

Introduction

In the Digital Industries as search engine optimization, search engine marketing (SAM), content marketing, influencer marketing, content automation, campaign marketing and e-commerce marketing, social network marketing, optimization of social media, e-mail marketing, view ads, e-bookings, optical disking or gaming our advanced technologies are becoming increasingly popular. This applies in fact to non-Internet channels including digital media such as mobile telephones (SMS and MMS), call-backs and ring sounds.

Digital marketing was first used in the 90s but digital marketing was established in the mid-80s when the Soft Ad Company, now Channel Net, launched automotive advertising campaigns to send the reader's answer cards to magazines and to receive disc records containing multimedia contents that promoted various cars and supplied free test drives.

The growth of smartphone connectivity in new media has almost often contributed to an important increase in digital advertising; figures generated in 2012 and 2013 show that digital marketing continues to grow. Digital marketing is also the word 'online marketing,' 'internet marketing' and 'blog marketing.' Digital marketing has increased over time in use, especially in some countries. Internet marketing remains dominant in the United States, while online marketing remains well known in Italy, digital marketing, particularly after 2013, is the most common concept in the UK and around

the globe. Digital advertising development in 2010 is expected to generate 4.5 trillion Internet ads, with an average increase of 48% in investment in digital media in 2010. The proportion of ads come from online behavioural advertising (OBA) companies for advertising aimed at Internet users, but OBA questions on customer confidentiality and data protection [2].

Current non-linear marketing approach

In an increasingly dynamic retail environment, customer loyalty is important yet demanding. Retailers could move from a one-way linear marketing strategy to a paradigm for value sharing in which suppliers and customers express their desires in a two-way reciprocal discussion. Trading is more non-linear, open and one-to-one. Knowledge and visibility will spread through a wide range of outlets including the blogosphere, YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat and Pinterest. Online forums and social networks make it easier for individuals to develop views, perspectives, thoughts and emotions and to speed up the distribution of knowledge on a range of topics and goods.

In 26 countries, the Nielsen Global Linked Marketplace Survey conducted interviews with Internet users in shops and online shopping. They have shown that shoppers are increasingly buying international goods through internet and e-commerce, with over 50 percent of them digitally purchasing from an overseas distributor in the past six months.

With an omni-channel approach, companies are increasingly necessary to meet changing customer demands, where the Internet is central to delivering increasingly complex goods. Retailers are increasingly relying on their online footprint, such as online retailers that match established stores.

This complements the concept of "endless aisle" in the retail region as retailers lead buyers to digitally purchase goods that meet their needs, without having to physically hold the stocks in the store. Only internet-based retailers join the market, and others construct suitable retail outlets to provide personal resources, technical support and meaningful product experiences [3].

An omnibus strategy helps both shoppers and businesses, as data shows that customers invest more than twice in shopping from an omnibus store in comparison with one-channel retailers and are more loyal to shopping. This could be due to rapid purchase and increased product choice with an omni-channel strategy.

Buyers often read digitally, buy and check in shops and then look for additional options online. Online customer analysis is particularly common in higher end products and household goods like food and compounds. Consumers increasingly use the Internet to find product details, compare prices and find sales and promotions.

Use in modern times

There are a variety of areas where brands can use digital marketing to gain their campaigns. Digital media use in the digital age not only helps marketers promote their products and services, but also allows consumers to feel digitally welcomed and valued by 24-hour services.

Using social networking, marketers can gain both constructive and critical information from their consumers to decide what media channels do best for them and it has been increasingly valuable for brands and organisations. It is now a popular practise for clients to publish online reviews on their product or brand experience through social networking outlets, blogs and websites. Organizations are becoming more frequent in using these interactions to communicate directly with consumers through their social networking platforms and to handle reviews properly.

Mouth-to-peer contacts and dialogues that are not sent directly from the organisation and are therefore not scheduled will also have a further impact on consumers. Customers are most likely to believe other customers' views. It is increasingly beneficial for companies to use social networking channels in order to connect and develop these dialogues and dialogues with their consumers. The future effects of social networking suggest that the Facebook application had over 126 million unique users per month in 2015, compared to over 97 million unique users per month [4].

Knowing the brand

A key objective is to involve and encourage digital marketers to communicate with the brand by maintaining and distributing digital media. Knowledge from digital communications is easily accessible.

Web-based users can use a wide range of interactive platforms such as Twitter, YouTube, forums, email etc. It provides a multimedia platform through digital communication that allows knowledge to be communicated instantly across the globe, irrespective of who it is. Racial discrimination is not a factor in social networking because a selective audience does not have face-to-face contact or knowledge. The immersive aspect helps customers to enter into dialogue in order to ask questions about the company and to find out what conventional forms of communication cannot provide.

Competitive gain

By using Internet channels, companies can build strategic advantages by different methods. Companies use social networking as their key weapons to build a knowledge platform to optimise the power of digital marketing. This helps an organisation develop a framework that recognises consumer behaviour trends and provides information on its specifications. This material showed a greater impact on people who have a long-standing connection to the company and relatively regular members on the social web.

Thus, the development of a social networking page will further improve the consistency of partnerships among potential clients and existing consumers as well as the continuous increase in brand recognition, thereby increasing customer awareness in the Brand Awareness Pyramid. Although product photos are incongruous; supporting a good social networking, a profile allows an organisation to work together to produce a two-way knowledge feed; companies consider the material on the basis of the input gained on this channel, and the world is complex because of the global existence of the Internet. In contrast to conventional marketing methods, successful use of digital media can result in a relatively low cost: lower external support costs, promotional cost, promotion costs, cost of production, interface design and control cost.

Effectiveness

Brand awareness in countries which are high in insecurity avoidance have proven to be more effective, including those that avoid uncertainty; social media marketing works effectively. Nevertheless, brands must take care not to overuse this type of marketing or to rely solely on it, because it could have consequences that could harm their image.

Brands that anthropomorphically represent themselves are more likely to succeed if a brand markets this demographic. "Since social media use can improve brand knowledge and thus reduce uncertainty, the high social media interaction with an anthropomorphized brand may particularly be appreciated by people with high levels of uncertainty, such as French people." Furthermore, the digital platform facilitates the brand and its customers' direct interactions and virtual exchange of motives.

Recent developments and policies

The « emergence of digital marketing», which led to the reinvention of marketing strategies to adapt to this major change in traditional marketing, was one of the main changes in the marketing industry.

As digital marketing depends on constantly changing and rapidly changing technology, the same features of digital marketing developments and strategies need to be anticipated. This portion attempts to qualify or separate the significant highlights which exist and are used as a press conference.

1. Segmentation:

more emphasis has been placed on digital marketing segmentation, with the goal of targeting specific markets in both the business to business and the consumer sectors.

2. Marketing of influencers:

In connected communities, known as influencers, important nodes are identified. This is an important concept in the field of digital targeting. Influencers can be reached through paid advertising, like Facebook or Google AdWords, or through sophisticated CRM software such as SAP C4C, Microsoft Dynamics, Sage CRM and Salesforce CRM. Many universities are now focusing on engagement strategies for influencers at Masters level.

In conclusion, pull digital marketing is characterised by consumers actively searching for marketing content while Push digital marketing occurs when commercials send messages without the receiver actively searching for this content.

Online behavioural promotion is a practise of collecting information about the online activity of a user on a given device and on different, unrelated websites over time in order to deliver advertising to the interests and preferences of that user.

Collaborative environment: The organisation, the technology services provider and the digital authorities can develop a collaborative environment to optimise effort, resource sharing, reusability and communication. In addition, organisations invite their customers to better understand how to serve them.

This data source is called Content Generated by the User. Much of this is acquired via websites of companies, in which the organisation invites people to share ideas which are then evaluated by other website users. The most popular ideas are

assessed and put into practise in some way. This method can encourage business relations with their customers and spawning ideas that would otherwise be overlooked by acquiring data and developing new products. UGC is cheap advertising, since it is directly available from the consumer and can reduce the company's advertising costs.

3. Data-driven advertising:

users generate a large number of data at each stage in the customer journey and Brands can now use that data to enable their knowledgeable audience to buy programmatic media driven by data. Without exposing the privacy of customers, users' Data can be gathered from digital channels (e.g.: when a customer visits a website, reads an e-mail or launches a brand mobile application), brands can also collect data from customer interactions in real-life situations, such as visits to brick and mortar shops and from CRM and Sales Engine datasets. Data-driven advertising, also known as People-based marketing or adressible media, empowers brands to find loyal customers within themselves and provide much more personal communication in real-time, which is extremely relevant to the moment and actions of each customer.

One important consideration today while deciding on a strategy is the democratisation of the promotional landscape by digital tools.

4. Remarketing :

In digital marketing, marketing plays a major role. This tactic allows marketers to publish targeted ads before an interest category or defined audience, usually called searchers in web speaks, searched or visited a website for specific products or services.

5. Game ads:

Game ads are ads that exist within computer or video games. Billboards that appear in sports games are one of the most common examples of in-game publicity. In-game ads may also appear as brand-name products, such as weapons, cars, or clothing available as game status symbols.

The new digital era has allowed brands to selectively target customers who may be interested in their brand or based on their previous browsing interests. Businesses can now use social media to select the age, location, gender and interests of the target audience. Moreover, based on a recent customer's search history, ads from similar brands, products and services can be "followed" on the internet; This allows companies to target customers that they know and feel will benefit most from their product or service, something that was limited to the digital era [5].

How to further improve digital marketing efficiency

Content marketing is a strategy linked to the effectiveness of digital marketing. Content marketing can be described briefly as "the provision of the content your audience is looking for in the places they are looking for." It is found that content marketing is highly present in digital marketing and very successful when it comes to content marketing. This is because content marketing makes your brand more relevant to target consumers and more visible to target customers.

Marketers also find e-mail an effective digital marketing strategy as it is another way of building a long-term relationship with consumers. The following are some aspects that need to be taken into account to create an efficient digital media campaign and to create an efficient email system.

Interesting mail titles distinguish one ad from the other. This separates ads from the mess. Differentiation is one factor which can make an ad a success in digital marketing as consumers are drawn to it and are more likely to view the ad.

Customer exclusivity establishment:

A list of customers and customer information should be kept in a follow-up database and selected customer offers and promotions related to customer's previous buyer behaviour. This is effective in digital marketing since it enables companies to build loyalty via e-mail.

Low technical needs:

In order to make full use of digital marketing, you have low technical requirements in advertising campaigns. This prevents some consumers from understanding or viewing the advertising campaign.

Rewards:

lucrative offers would always contribute to the success of your digital campaign. At the end of the campaign, give some reward. This would definitely call for more engagement and word of mouth

Digital marketing ineffective forms:

According to the headline global marketing index, digital marketing is still growing worldwide. Digital media continue to grow rapidly; as marketing budgets grow, traditional media decline (World Economics, 2015). Digital media helps brands reach consumers to personalise their products or services.

Five areas, often ineffective in current industry practises, are priority setting for clicking, balancing search and display, mobile understanding, targeting, viewing abilities, brand safety and invalid traffic, and cross platform measurement (Whiteside, 2016). The reasons why these practises are ineffective and certain ways to make these aspects effective are discussed in the following areas.

wherein strategies are made and executed to draw in traffic for a website or to gain attention of buyers over the web using different social media platforms.

Click Prioritization:

Clicks prioritisation means displaying click ads, although the benefit of 'simple, fast and cheap' rates for display ads in 2016 in the US is 0.10%. This means that one in one thousand click ads have little effect. This shows that marketing companies should not just use click ads to evaluate the efficiency of display ads (Whiteside, 2016).

Search and display balance:

It is important to balance the search and display for digital display ads; marketers tend to look at the last search and attribute all the effectiveness to it. This then overlooks other marketing efforts that set brand value in the mind of consumers.

ComScore has been determined by drawing on online data produced by over a hundred multi-channel retailers that digital display marketing provides strengths compared to or alongside paid search (Whiteside, 2016).

That is why it is advised that the company opens a landing page, not its home page when someone clicks on a display ad. A landing page usually has something for the client to look beyond this page. Things like free offers that the consumer can obtain from providing information to the company to use retargeting communications strategies (Square2Marketing, 2012). Marketers usually see higher sales among people who have a search ad. But consideration should be given to how many people you can reach with a display campaign in comparison with a search campaign. If the display is taken into account in synergy with search campaigns, multichannel retailers have an increased reach. In total, search and display aspects are appreciated when display campaigns raise brand awareness so that more people can click on these digital ads when running a search campaign (Whiteside, 2016).

Mobile Understanding:

Understanding mobile devices is an important aspect of digital marketing, as smart phones and tablets account for 64% of US consumers online (Whiteside, 2016). Apps provide the marketers with a great opportunity as well as a challenge, because the app has to be downloaded and the person has to use it in the first place.

This can be hard as 'half the time spent on smartphone apps is spent on individuals using the most widely used app, and nearly 85% on top four apps' (Whiteside, 2016). Mobile advertising can help to reach a variety of commercial objectives and is effective because the entire screen is covered, and voice or status is likely to be highly regarded; however, the message should not be seen or seen as intrusive (Whiteside, 2016). Digital media used on mobile devices also have limited creativity and reach. Although many positive aspects include the right of users to choose product information, digital media create a flexible message platform and direct sales potential [6].

Cross-platform measuring:

The number of marketing channels continues to grow with increasing complexity of measurement practises. To unify audience measurement and media planning, a cross-platform view must be used. Market researchers need to understand how the Omni channel affects consumer behaviour, although it is not measured when advertising is on a consumer device. Significant aspects for cross-platform measurement include deduplication and a realisation that with another platform you have reached an incremental level, rather than giving more impressions to previously reached people (Whiteside, 2016).

An example is 'ESPN and comScore partnered in Project Blueprint which, thanks to digital advertising, has achieved an increase of 21% in uncommodified daily reach' (Whiteside, 2016). TV and radio industries are electronic media competing with digital and other advertising technology. However, television ads don't compete directly with digital online advertising because they can cross platforms with digital technology. Radio also gains power in online streaming content through cross-platforms. Ferns Ehen and radio continue to convince and influence the audience on multiple platforms[7].

Targeting, ability to view, brand safety and invalid traffic: targeting, ability to view, brand safety and invalid traffic are all aspects that marketers use to advocate digital advertising. Cookies are a form of digital advertising that tracks tools in a desktop device; cause problems, weaknesses such as web browser deletion, inability to sort between multiple device users, inaccurate estimates for single visitors, excessive reach, frequency of understand ENT, problems with ad servers that do not distinguish between when cookies are deleted (Whiteside, 2016).

Another factor that is affected by digital marketing is "visibility," or whether the ad was actually viewed by the consumer. Many advertisements cannot be viewed by a consumer and may never reach the right population segment. Brand safety is another question of whether or not the ad is unethical or offensive in content. Another challenge for the marketer is recognising fraud when an ad is exposed. This applies to invalid traffic as premium sites are more effective in traffic detection, but non-premium sites are more problematic [7-12].

Channels

Multiple channels facilitate digital marketing, as an advertiser's central goal is to find channel solutions that result in maximum two-way communication and a better total brand ROI. Many online marketing channels are available, in particular;

- **Affiliate marketing** – Affiliate marketing is not considered a safe, reliable and easy means of online marketing. This is because of a lack of reliability for affiliates which can generate the required number of new customers. Because of this risk and bad affiliates, it leaves the brand to be exploited as a result of a commission that is not honestly acquired.

Legal means can provide some protection against it, but the recovery of losses or investment is restricted. However, affiliate marketing allows the brand to market to smaller publishers and smaller websites. Brands that choose to use this marketing should often take care of these risks and should seek to associate themselves with the companies in which the rules between the parties concerned are laid down to ensure and minimise the risk involved.

Display advertising

Email marketing – Email marketing is considered cheap in comparison with other forms of digital marketing; it is also the way to quickly transmit an email message to existing or potential clients, such as their value proposition. Yet recipients can perceive this communication channel to be mischievous and irritating especially for new or potential customers, hence the success of email marketing depends on the language and visual appeal. With regard to the visual call, there are indications that using graphics/visuals that relate to the message being sent but fewer visual graphics for initial emails are more efficient in-turn, creating a relatively personal feeling for the email.

The style is the main factor when determining how captivating the e-mail is in terms of language. The casual tone invokes a warmer, gentle and inviting feeling to the e-mail compared to a formal style. For combinations; to maximise efficiency; without using

graphics or visuals alongside casual language. In contrast, the least effective method is to use no visual appeal and a formal language style.

Search marketing - Social media marketing - Search marketing - The term 'digital marketing' has a number of marketing aspects because it supports various channels in which Social Media is used. The Strategy is called Social Media Marketing when using social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, Pinterest, Instagram, Google+, etc.) to market a product or service. It's a process

Social connectivity

Game advertising—In-Game advertising is defined as "including in a digital game products or brands." The game allows brands or products, either in a subtle way or in the form of publicity banners, to place ads within their game.

There are many factors that influence the success of the brands in their brand/product advertising: game type, technical platform, 3D and 4D technology, game genre, brand and game congruity, advertising prominence in this game. Individual factors include attitudes towards advertising, gambling, product engagement, flow or entertainment. The attitude to advertising also takes into consideration not only the message, but also the attitude to the game. Depending on how pleasant the game is, the perception of the brand is determined and the consumer can subconsciously have a negative attitude against the brand / product being advertised if the game is not very enjoyable. The "integration of advertising in the digital games into the company's general advertising, communication, and marketing strategy" is an important communication in terms of integrated marketing because it provides more clarity about the brand/product and a broader global effect [8–9].

Online Public Relations

1. Video advertising — Digital/online advertising is an ad that plays on online videos e.g. YouTube. 1. Over time, this type of marketing has gained popularity.

The online video ad usually consists of three types: Pre-Roll ads played before the video is viewed, Mid-Roll ads played during the video or Post-Roll ads played after viewing the video. Post-roll ads were shown to be better recognised by brands compared to other types, whereas "congruity/incongruity ad context plays an important role in enforcing ad memorability." Because of the viewers' selective attention, the message may not be received. Video advertising's main advantage is that it interferes with the viewing experience of the video and therefore it is difficult to avoid it. How a consumer interacts with online video ads can take three steps: Precaution, care and decision about behaviour.

These online ads offer brand/business options and choices. These consist of longitude, position and adjacent video content that directly affect the effectiveness of the advertising time produced so that manipulation of these variables results differently. The length of the advertisement has been shown to influence memorability, with longer duration leading to increased brand identification. Due to the nature of the viewer's interruption, such advertising may make the consumer feel like their experience has been interrupted or invaded, which creates a negative perception of the mark. These ads are also available for viewers to share, adding to the attractiveness of this platform.

The sharing of these videos can be compared to the online word marketing version, which reaches large numbers of people. The sharing of videos produces six different results: "pleasure, affection, inclusion, escape, relaxation and control." Videos with entertainment value are also more likely to be shared, yet pleasure is the main motivator for passing on videos. The creation of a "viral" trend from the mass of a brand ad can maximise the effect of an online video ad, be it positive or negative.

It is important for a company to reach the consumer and create a two-way communication model because digital marketing allows consumers to return feeds to the company via email to a community-based site or directly to the company. Companies should seek this long-term communication relationship through the application of multiple channels and promotional strategies related to their target consumer, and word of mouth marketing. [12-15] [12-15]

Self-control

The ICC Code has integrated rules for marketing communications throughout the guidelines through digital interactive media. There is also a fully updated section dealing with digital interactive media and platform issues. Self-regulation code on the use of interactive digital media covers:

- Clear and transparent mechanisms in order to ensure that consumers do not choose to collect their data for ads or marketing purposes;
- Clear evidence that the social network site is commercial and is under the control or influence of marketers;
- Limits to marketers' communications only when there are reasonable grounds to believe that consumers are interested in what

Benefits and limitations

In the general communication between the consumer and the organisation, the whole idea of digital marketing can be very important. This is due to the fact that digital marketing can reach a large number of potential consumers at once.

Another advantage of digital marketing is that consumers are directly exposed to the brand and product. The advertisement is easy to access to clarify and can be accessed anytime. However, there are some setbacks to this type of strategy with digital marketing. One of the major setbacks is that digital marketing relies heavily on the internet.

This could be regarded as a setback because in some areas the Internet cannot be accessible or because consumers have poor internet access.

Along with digital marketing, which is highly dependent on the Internet, it is subject to a lot of clutter, so marketers can find it difficult to make their announcements stand out, as well as to encourage consumers to engage in discussions regarding a brand image or product organization [9-14].

As digital marketing continues to grow and develop, brands benefit greatly from the use of technology and the internet to communicate with their customers and to increase the reach of who they can interact with and how they do so. However, disadvantages are not frequently considered because of how much a business relies on them. For marketers, it is important for their marketing strategy and business objectives to take into account the advantages and disadvantages of digital marketing [10-12].

The advantage of digital marketing is that its reach is so wide that the geographical reach cannot be limited. This allows companies to become international and expand customer reach to countries other than the country from which they are based or originate. As already mentioned, technology and the internet provide customer service 24 hours a day, 7 days a week and allow customers to shop online at any time of day or night, not just when shops are all over the world.

For retailers this is a great advantage and directs customers from the store to their online store. It has also given companies the chance of being based only online rather than having outlets or shops because of its popularity and digital marketing capabilities [15-17].

Another benefit is that digital marketing is easy to measure and allow companies to know whether their marketing works or not, and the amount of activity and conversation involved. Brands that use the Internet to reach their target customers have also become a beneficial career option for digital marketing. Companies are currently engaging people who are familiar with the implementation of digital marketing strategies, which has made the stream a preferred choice for individuals who inspire institutes who offer professional courses in Digital Marketing.

The large number of competing products and services that use the same digital marketing strategies is a disadvantage to digital advertising. For example, if someone looks for a particular product from a specific company online, if a similar company uses targeted online advertising, they can appear on the client's home page so that customers can look at alternatives to a cheaper price or quality of the same product and find their desires more quickly online [18].

Some companies may be negatively illustrated by customers as some consumers lack confidence online because of the amount of advertising on websites and social media that may be considered fraudulent. This can influence your image and reputation and make it look like a dishonest brand.

Another disadvantage is that even an individual or small group of individuals can damage the image of a brand. For example, Doppelganger is a term used to disapprove of an image that is presented by anti-brand activists, bloggers and opinion leaders of a certain brand. The word "doppelganger" means the combination of two German words "double" (double) and the word "ganger" (walker). Brand generally creates images for itself to attract its customers emotionally. Some would not agree with this picture, alter it, and show it in a funny or cynical way, thereby distorting the brand image and creating an image, blog or content of Doppelganger [19-20].

In the case of digital marketing, two further practical limitations can be seen. Digital marketing is useful for specific product categories, which means that digital channels can only promote consumer goods. Digital channels cannot be used to market industrial goods and pharmaceuticals. Secondly, digital marketing only distributes information to the prospects most of whom do not have buying power. The fact that digital marketing is reflected in real sales volumes is therefore sceptical [21].

Conclusions:

Although return on investment or any other financial metrics in general should constitute the final criteria for evaluating any business initiative, the assessment criteria

and metrics for digital marketing campaigns are discussed more in detail. The criteria and metrics can be classified by type and time. Regarding the type, we can "quantitatively" or "qualitatively" evaluate these campaigns. "Sales volume" and "income increase or decline" may include quantitative metrics. Although qualitative metrics may include improved "brand awareness, image and health" as well as "customer relationships." If we are to concentrate on time, we may have to measure some Interim Metrics to give us insights during the trip itself and also some "Final Metrics" to measure at the end of the trip in order to inform us if the overall initiative has been successful or not.

For example, most social media metrics and indicators such as likes, shares and comments can be classified as interim metrics, whereas the last sales volume increases / decreases are clearly defined in the final category. Of course, there should be a correlation between these categories. Otherwise, disappointing results can eventually occur despite the illusion that the project is successful early.

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ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

Creativity and innovations are indispensable for the growth of business and the success of the organization. It is an important factor which helps traditional companies and educational institutions in foreseeing the potential threats and rising competition. Needless to say, companies and organizations cannot thrive without matching the pace with the change and transformation which is taking place in the market. Digital transformation integrates digital technologies into all areas of a business. To meet with the ever changing demands of business processes and customer expectations and create a competitive advantage as well as positioning the organization for the future growth, the role of digital transformation and innovation cannot be ignored. IoT, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Automation, Machine Learning, Block Chain are some of the latest technologies which have brought about the sea of change by amalgamating demanding millennial generation into the high speed data lanes. In the past few months of Lockdown, digitalization has played a vital role in sustaining the global economic condition. Businesses are now looking for the new ways of dealings and cost minimization. Educational institutions also embraced digital mode of teaching and learning methodologies in order to minimize the impact of pandemic on the academics of students. This conference is intended to seek intellectual contribution of experts from industry, academia and research for embracing change & transformation through innovations and creativity.

ABOUT US

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School runs AICTE approved PGDM program. It has been ranked 1st Emerging B-School among top institutes of west India by Time of India. It has also been conferred the ET Now Business School of the year award. The two-year full-time PGDM program offered by Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School is designed to empower students to become successful business professionals in the challenging global scenario. The Institute is continually evolving to meet its goals in an ever-changing business environment. It has been playing an important role in professionalizing Indian Management through its programs. Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School aims to create value-driven leaders, global managers and entrepreneurs with strong conceptual foundations and analytical approach to help them be the best in whichever field they choose. The aim is to innovatively address the needs of a modern India and connecting aspirations and realities to attain benchmarks that are respected internationally.

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